

application and resists lodging. It is relatively tolerant of low temperature at meiosis and flowering. Leaves are light green and become yellowish-green during ripening. It has had few disease and insect problems. Yield is comparatively stable.

Hang Feng has superior grain quality and high milling percentage. Milled rice is broad, uniform, and white, with good flavor, suitable stickiness, good scent, and glossy appearance.

The variety is most commonly planted as a second crop (plant height 70-75 cm),

although it also is single-cropped (plant height 85-90 cm). Second crop growth duration is 140 d. A single crop takes about 160 d. Hang Feng yields about 5 t/ha as a second crop and may yield 30% more in a single-cropping system. \mathcal{L}

Performance of BW rices in the midcountry wet zone of Sri Lanka

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We evaluated 5 short-duration (90-100 d) BW rices for performance in the Sri Lanka midcountry wet zone (MZ) at Peradeniya in Jul-Oct 1982. BW272-6B, BW288-2, BW293-2, BW267-3, and BW267-7 were developed by the Bombuwela Regional Agricultural Research Station (BRARS) for the low country wet zone, mainly the Kalutara Galle and Matara districts.

Plant height, 1,000-grain weight, yield, number of productive tillers, and panicle length in the MZ were compared with similar data from BRARS, where the varieties were grown in Apr-Jun 1982 (see table). Fertilizer doses were the same at both sites.

Peradeniya is 490 m above sea level and Bombuwela is 3 m above sea level. Average monthly temperature and rainfall at the sites are in the figure. The

Performance of BW rices at Peradeniya and BRARS.^a

Variety	Plant ht (cm)		Productive tillers (no.)		Panicle length (cm)		1000-grain wt (g)		Grain wt per plant	
	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B
BW 272-6B	102.8	100.5	2.4	5.0	25.6	26.36	16.1	16.7	4.02	5.75
BW 288-2	52.3	66.51	3.3	4.0	16.1	20.4	27.7	29.8	4.78	8.60
BW 293-2	59.0	66.01	1.9	3.0	9.5	22.8	27.2	30.0	3.21	7.80
BW 267-3	75.8	77.09	2.1	5.0	22.1	20.08	30.1	30.6	4.49	9.20
BW 266-7	94.0	81.56	2.2	4.0	21.8	21.71	25.4	25.8	2.03	5.68

^a P = av of 60 plants (20/replication) were analyzed at Peradeniya. B = data obtained from BRARS.

Monthly precipitation and temperature in Bombuwela and Peradeniya, Sri Lanka. 1982.

soil at Peradeniya is an alluvial gley.

The varieties performed poorly in the MZ, and took longer to mature than at BRARS. BW272-6B, normally a 90-d variety, matured in 122 d. All the varieties retained their insect and diseases resistance. BW267-3 yielded highest at both sites.

The differences in yield and maturity may have been caused by differences in location, that could have attributed to differences in humidity, sunshine hours, rainfall, day-night temperature, and irrigation water quality. \mathcal{L}

Manhar, high yielding, early maturing rice for the irrigated plains of Uttar Pradesh

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Manhar (UPR103-44-2) was developed using the pedigree method after hybridization of IR24 and Cauvery. It is a semidwarf that matures in 123 d, and is suitable for the irrigated plains of Uttar Pradesh.

Table 1. Mean performance of Manhar in trials in Uttar Pradesh, India.

Trial ^a	Year	Mean yield (t/ha)			
		Manhar	Saket 4 (check)	Prasad (check)	Increase ^b (%) over check
VT-Early	1980	5.1	4.3	4.2	18
VT-Early	1981	4.5	—	4.3	3
VT-Early	1982	4.9	—	4.1	20
VT-Early	1983	4.6	—	4.3	5
VT-Early	1984	4.8	—	4.4	10
SVT-Early	1982	4.8	3.9	—	22
SVT-Early	1983	4.3	3.7	—	15
SVT-Early	1984	3.7	3.2	—	18
PVT-2 (AICRIP)	1982	4.9	3.3	Ratna	49
PTV-2 (AICRIP)	1983	3.1	2.3	Rasi	34
Mean Sites (no.)		4.6	3.9	4.2	
		61	29	33	

^a VT = Varietal Trials, SVT = Standard Varietal Trials, PVT = All India Coordinated Trials. ^b Mean of 17% over Saket 4, 8% over Prasad.